

Scheme 2

EXPERIMENTAL

All melting points were taken on a Thomas-Hoover capillary melting point apparatus and are uncorrected.

1,1-Dimethyl-4-phenylthiosemicarbazide (I) was prepared by heating under reflux an ethanolic solution of equimolar amounts of 1,1-dimethyl-hydrazine and phenyl isothiocyanate. M.P. 184° and 187–88° after recrystallization from ethanol; lit.⁴ 188°.

2-Dimethylamino-imino-3-phenyl-4-thiazolidinone (II): A mixture of 1,1-dimethyl-4-phenylthiosemicarbazide (I) (10 g., 0.05 mole), chloroacetic acid (5.2 g., 0.055 mole), and freshly fused sodium acetate (5.7 g., 0.07 mole) in 100 ml. of absolute ethanol was heated under reflux for 6 hrs. The mixture was added to 250 ml. of water. The colourless solid that precipitated was collected by filtration with suction, washed with water and air-dried. Yield 12 g., 100% crude. Recrystallization from ethanol gave colourless leaflets melting at 176°. Mixed with 1,1-dimethyl-4-phenylthiosemicarbazide, the melting point was depressed to 148°. Anal. Calcd. for C₁₁H₁₃N₃OS : C, 56.17; H, 5.53 : Found : C, 56.51; H, 5.69.

Hydrolysis of II : To a mixture of 10 ml. of concentrated sulphuric acid and 25 ml. of water was added 2 g., of II. The mixture was heated under reflux for 2 hrs. and left overnight at room temperature. A colourless crystalline solid was deposited. Collected by filtration with suction and washed with cold water, it weighed 0.2 g. Recrystallization from ethanol gave colourless needles melting at 143–44°. A mixed melting point with 3-phenyl-2,4-thiazolidinedione, m.p. 144°, prepared from thiocarbanilide according to Lange⁵, was not depressed.

Department of Chemistry,
St Xavier's College,
Ahmedabad-9.

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4. R. S. Levy, *Mem. Poudres*, 1955, 40, 429; *C.A.*, 1959, 65, 19539.
5. A. Lange, *Chem. Ber.*, 1879, 12, 597.